

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10862924>

HOW LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES CAN HELP STUDENTS BE INTERCULTURAL COMPETENT?

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the importance of learning different languages in order to be intercultural competent and develop socio skills.

Key words: *Competence – types of competence, foreign language learning, language patterns, students' viewpoint.*

Introduction

Every sphere of human development should be encouraged by people. People's experience, work, level of education and competence. The last is one of the main aspects of any development, whether it is business industry or education.

What is competence? The quality or state of having sufficient knowledge, judgment, skill, or strength (as for a particular duty or in a particular respect). According to Oxford Languages Dictionary : competence is the ability to do something successfully or efficiently. Do we need just competence? Or are there specific types of the competence, some of which we can use in self development?

Main part

3 types of competence can be discussed as the main ones: linguistic competence, communicative competence and intercultural competence.

- Linguistic competence

In this type of competence explained how one can use range of grammar, vocabulary with coherence and cohesion of particular language, it can be a mother tongue or a target one. Moreover, the ability of teaching one language to students is also considered to be a part of linguistic competence.

- Communicative competence

This type of competence shows up the ability of correct usage of different types of oral and written communication, such as: formal, informal speaking and writing, in the correct time and situation when it is required.

- Intercultural competence

On the other hand this type of competence is the most important one. Because in order to be intercultural competent one should know the language (linguistic competence), should know the correct usage of it (communicative competence). That is why this competence includes other main competencies. Specifically, learning different foreign languages enhanced, does and will enhance the students' viewpoint to the life. So how does it work?

The main reason is the information that person consumes. For instance, one student knows 2 languages - mother tongue and foreign one: this student can watch both L1-based videos, movies, talk shows, etc. Also, they can watch entertaining or scientific videos on Language 2. This shows that this student is aware of more information (which can be more entertaining and professional) than the student who knows just one language. On the other hand, this student is able to read the literature works, history of country (in which a particular language is used) which enhances the range of knowledge, intellectual and critical thinking. A striking example is the Korean language. When learning the Korean language, we study the details, nuances and traditions of the Koreans. For example, when greeting, a younger person should bend

a little lower than an older person. Even while eating, you should not place chopsticks vertically on your food – this is believed that it will bring bad things for Koreans. Koreans respect their elders very much, this can be learned while learning the Korean language in contexts and different social networks, since when you are with elders, you cannot sit with your legs bent and you cannot use your index finger while talking to them. Knowing the Korean language, students will be ready for different situations when working with Koreans, for example. But those who do not know the Korean language will not actually know such features of Korean culture. So this is why knowledge of a language is closely related to culture. In such a way as to understand the world from different perspectives one need to know many foreign languages.

Additionally, as it is said: “ One language sets you in a corridor for life, two languages open you all the doors along the way”. This proverb has deep meaning and notion, that being able to know, understand and use foreign languages will definitely open a bunch of opportunities for being competent.

Conclusion

When one learns a new language, the traditions, customs and the whole culture patterns are also studied. Because we cannot ignore the culture of the language being taught. According to this fact, if one knows 3 languages this person is aware of 3 different cultures – 3 different viewpoints for life. That is basis of being intercultural competent.

Being intercultural competent can hold over and save from different intercultural misunderstandings, which is not pleasant and can seem impolite in some situations. In order to be intercultural competent the language learning process is very crucial. All things considered, after having learned a foreign language, the literature, mass media and film industry of this language is applied and by ourselves even without knowing it.

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